

EVALUATION OF THE FACTORS AFFECTING SMALLHOLDER RICE FARMERS' USE OF ICTS TO ACCESS MARKET INFORMATION IN THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY, ABUJA, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the variables affecting smallholder farmers' usage of information and communication technologies to get market information in Abuja. Data were gathered via an organized questionnaire and 120 respondents were surveyed in a cross-sectional research methodology. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were applied to the data analysis. Results showed that 50.7% of farmers use their mobile phones as their primary information source, with 83.3% of farmers having access to ICTs. According to the cross-tabulation results (Chi-square test), the availability of ICTs sources of information had an upward, significant ($P \leq 0.05$), and positive relationship with marital status, sex, and income level. The survey indicated that just 45% of farmers who have access to ICTs as a source of information use the technology to get market information, with awareness, limited access, and weak networks posing the biggest obstacles. The logit model's findings show that the farmers' sex, education level, income level, knowledge about ICT sources of information, and access to those sources are all highly significant ($P \leq 0.05$) variables that influence farmers' use of ICTs at the 5% significant level. These results lead to the conclusion that the mobile phone is the ICT source of information which is used the most in rural regions. Additionally, the majority of Abuja's smallholder farmers are unaware of the advantages of using ICT to get market information. In order to enable farmers access market information, increase the accessibility of dependable power sources, and open up new markets, the government and other agricultural stakeholders should find a means to teach and inform them about new technology. Additionally, network providers ought to expand their services in remote places with strong signals.

Key Words: ICT, market, information, rice, smallholders

INTRODUCTION

The agricultural sector has periodically performed an important part in alleviating poverty in a number of nations that are about how to develop, but there are still critical arguments to be addressed about how to properly support the sector's expansion today. According to Ayoola and Ayoola (2015), agricultural development in the private sector grew slowly. Numerous rural areas in contrast to how quickly agricultural liberalization continued. This converts into an issue for tying

private sector development to goals of reducing poverty and providing social security for underprivileged and marginalized populations when it comes to policy guidance and dissemination. Furthermore, it is becoming more frequently understood that the provision of core public goods (social and environmental) can enhance instead of inhibit market growth. Establishing institutions that encourage markets and better control growth is a priority in response in response to the necessity to "make markets work for the poor".

Specifically, through enhancing impoverished farmers' access to markets, reducing and managing market-related risk, and recognizing the distinct benefits of various agricultural sector segments (Sennuga, Baines, Conway and Naylor, 2020).

Over the past thirty years, the significance of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) has been extensively addressed (Qaim and Sekabira, 2017). ICT can aid in successfully implementing new agricultural policies and practices, as well as those in related fields. ICT is a broadened term for information technology (IT) that emphasizes the significance of integrated communication and the merging of telecommunications (telephone lines and wireless signals), computers, and the requisite enterprise software, middleware, storage, and audio-visual systems that allow users to access, retrieve, distribute, and handle information (Adofu, Abula and Audu, 2017; Ajayi, Alabi and Akinsola, 2018). When discussing ICT, the study will solely be focused on mobile phones, the internet, radio, and television. E-commerce first appeared in the business world in the 1990s (Shahriari, Shhriari, and Ghejj, 2015; Chavula, 2017), and with the internet's recent rapid development and its promotion of trade globalization as a whole, it has gained a new power that is having an impact on how businesses market themselves (Conger, 2015). The main driver of agricultural development has been product marketing (Francis, 2016).

Despite the significance of the market, a company's or farmer's capacity to utilize current marketing strategies (listening and watching various TV and radio news regarding agriculture market information) depends greatly on institutional and individual variables. In embracing various new marketing channels which include agricultural E-commerce (Musah, Bonsu, and Seini, 2014). Agricultural E-commerce supports various business models, such as multi-supplier, e-sales, and also different types of auctions, enabling good trading opportunities and potential while traditional marketing

systems were unable to keep up with changing market trends (Irungu, Mbugua and Muia, 2015; Folorunso, Shushil, Sharma, Longe and Lasaki, 2016). In a similar vein, Widadie and Agustono (2015) asset as cited by Urassa and Mvena (2015) that ICT in Swaziland has made it possible for livestock owners to gain access to a variety of marketplaces and trade cattle more effectively. Due to the connection between ICT, which includes mobile phones, the internet, radio, and television, the effectiveness of the agriculture sector has improved significantly (Lucky and Achebe, 2015; Sennuga, Conway and Sennuga, 2020).

At the level of businesses and individual farmers who participate in production or service provision, the current creative in information technology development serves to solve social, organizational, and economic challenges. In Nigeria, the mobile phone industry is one of the ones that is expanding the fastest in relation to customers, service providers, and service variety. Nigeria reported 40.08 million mobile phone customers as of the end of 2016 and seven different service providers, including Mtn, Airtel, Glo etc (Sennuga, 2019). Nigeria now has 45% more internet users than it did in 2012 (17% vs. 45%) (Agwu and Ogbonnah, 2016). Only 44.1% and 24% of farmers have knowledge of and use ICT services in their respective agricultural activities, rice and maize, notwithstanding the proliferation of several online services that allow users to access social media (Bolarinwa and Oyeyinka, 2021; Ayeni, Sennuga, Bamidele, Alabuja and Osho-Lagunju, 2023).

In addition, Tomar, Verma, Ranjan, Bharwdaj, and Bhati (2015) observed that as a result of transaction costs and other reasons, proximity to the market has a major negative impact on the choice of the farmer to engage and the farmer's level of market participation. As they impede effective marketing and reduce farmers' income, poor infrastructure, low market pricing, as well as restricted access to market information pose significant deterrents for farmers in developing countries. Additionally, the inability to gather

information and the pervasive issue of disparity in information among farmers and buyers which both been connected to the collapse of agricultural markets for little businesses and smallholder farmers. Prior research in Nigeria (Fabusoro and Ajayi, 2015; Okeke, Hyacinth, Nwaleji and Uzuegbunam, 2015) has mostly concentrated about the function, importance, and use of ICT in agriculture by farmers. Understanding the factors impacting farmers' acceptance and usage of ICT is so crucial. This will help to bridge the to address the knowledge gap, this study will assess the variables that influence how Abuja residents use ICT to get market information. The specific of objectives are to:

- i. describe the socio-economic characteristics of smallholder rice farmers in Abuja.
- ii. Identify the ICT's sources of information accessed by the rice farmers and factors influencing the access of ICT services among smallholder rice farmers.
- iii. assess the factors influencing the use of Information and Communication Technologies in accessing market information among smallholder rice farmers in Abuja.
- iv. identify challenges encountered by smallholder rice farmers when accessing market information.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This research was carried out in the FCT, Abuja. It is located between longitudes 6° 46' and 7° 37' East of Greenwich and latitudes 8° 25' and 8° 25' North of the equator. The Federal Capital Territory has a total area of over 8,000 km², a height of about 536 m above sea level, and a population of 776,298 according to the 2006 census. Four states around it on all sides: Kogi, Niger, Nasarawa, and Kaduna. Six district councils make up Abuja: Abaji, Bwari, Gwagwalada, Kuje, Kwali, and the Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC). Given the

abundance of the northern Guinea Savannah Grassland and Middle Belt, it has a tropical southern forest climate. Due to its favourable environment, the National Capital has good agricultural land. The annual precipitation total ranges between 1100 to 1600 millimetres. The dry season stays at a certain duration of time from October to April and the wet season from April to October, with an average temperature of 290 degrees Celsius. Because of the area's high altitude and sloping landscape, the weather is moderated.

Population and sample selection

The population of interest for the study is Abuja, Nigeria's smallholder rice growers. The study, which employed simple random sampling, required a total sample size of 120 rice farmers from the six Area Councils.

Methods of data collection and analysis

This study relied on primary data acquired by utilizing a structured survey to fulfill the goals it established. To collect data, enumerators delivered a standardized questionnaire to smallholder rice growers.

Descriptive and inferential statistics utilized the data analysis. The socio-economic features of the rice farmers were outlined using descriptive statistics, which included frequency distribution, means, cross tabulation, and percentages. The informational ICT source that the farmers used was also identified. Descriptive analysis and logistic regression (Odds ratio results) were also used to demonstrate the extent of ICT usage in rice marketing. The extent of usage was evaluated using a scale ranging from very high to very low uses, with the mean used to determine rankings (Tomar *et al.*, 2016). According to Achandi and Mujawamariya (2016), the logit regression model was employed to calculate the results of ICT usage on rice marketing information availability.

Logit model

It employed the logit model to analyze the determinant factors impacting the adoption of ICT in rice marketing. This approach is being

used to find factors impacting how individuals use technology in various social-economic studies (Omair, 2016). Because the dependent variable in this study is

dichotomous (binary), that is, (Y0 and Y1), logistic regression was chosen as the proper regression approach to execute. The function of the model is described as follows:

$$p_i = 1/[1 + \exp(-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_k X_k))] \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

P_i = the probability of enhanced market structures and improved conduct among marketers

β_0 = Constant term in the expression, β_1 = unknown coefficient to be estimated, X_k = for $K=1, \dots, 9$, which are independent variables and i = i th observation. The model will be linearized as the right-hand side a logit transformation was applied by taking logarithm of both sides as:

$$\text{Log } P(Y_i) = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_{ik} X_{ik} + u \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where; Y_i = (1 using ICT) and β_0 is a constant term in the equation and β_i = unknown coefficient to be estimated and X_{ik} = Independent variables

X_1 = Age

X_2 = Gender

X_3 = Educational attainment (number of years in school)

X_4 = Sources of market information,

X_5 = Annual income of the individuals

X_6 = Presence of regulatory bodies

X_7 = level of awareness of the farmer

X_8 = Expenses associated with marketing activities

X_9 = Source of power

X_{10} = Accessibility

U = Unobserved factors and measurement errors

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-Economic Characteristics for Rice Farmers in the study area

According to Table 1, the age range of 21 to 40 years old made up most of the respondents, subsequently, the age range of 41 to 60 years old with 34.2%. No respondents under the age of 20 participated in the survey since most respondents are students enrolled in elementary, secondary, or university education. There were just 2.5% of participants who were 61 or older. This demonstrates that youthful farmers exhibit

higher adaptability, and easier to change than other groups, and most of Abuja's rice farmers are mid-aged farmers. Previous studies show that youthful farmers demonstrate greater productivity, and are more ready and prepared than other age groups to invest more time in learning about new technology (Folorunso *et al.*, 2016).

According to Table 1, just 41.7% of farmers were women, with 58.3% of farmers being men. Due to the fact that males made up nearly all household head who participated in this study. This is a common occurrence in African custom, where a husband is often the head of

the household and it is uncommon for women to own resources for production like land and money. As a result, farmers who are men are more than female farmers who will possess access to and use ICTs. The article claims that the majority of Abuja's rice farmers (60.8%) were married. Accordingly, 5.1%, 20.8%, and 13.3% of the respondents were either widowed or divorced, or single respectively. Because most of the respondents were above the age of 21, the study's findings that a large percentage of them were married as a result. This implies that the vast majority of these respondents work in farming to fulfill their responsibilities, to assure food availability and raise their income for other essential family requirements. However, Table 2 findings also demonstrate a high divorce rate of 20.8%, which accounts for the extremely low distinction between the proportion of male farmers and female farmers (16.6%). According to Table 1 survey results, 79.2% of farmers reported having finished primary school, while 14.2% and 1.6% completed their secondary and higher education. about 5% of people lacked any kind of formal education. This indicates that the research area includes both literate and uneducated rice farmers apart from those who are literate. Those who lack formal education primarily use their expertise in the process of trading their rice, which may impede farmers' access

to ICT for effective marketing, those with primary education and beyond, including higher levels of education comprehend the significance of market information and the utilization of ICT for obtaining that information (Falola and Ajayi, 2015). As shown in Table 2, the majority of rice farmers have between 11 and 20 years of experience, or 33.3%, and those with fewer than 10 years of experience respectively. Only 1.8% of rice farmers have more than 40 years of experience, trailed by 18.3% and 13.3% of farmers with 21 to 30 and 31 to 40 years of experience, respectively. This demonstrates that most rice farmers possess limited experience in the industry, as a result, they necessitate additional information about the industry and the market environment to help them with agricultural practices, farmer communication, and market research, particularly when using ICT.

According to survey findings, most respondents (57.5%) were growing farming less than 3 acres of rice, while 39.2% of rice farmers owned between 4 and 7 acres, and just 3.3% of rice farmers owned more than 7 acres, as indicated in Table 2. This suggests that Abuja's farmers are primarily small-scale. Therefore, both small- and large-scale farmers can readily choose to employ ICT as an information source (Ayoola *et al.*, 2015).

Table 1: Socio-Economic Characteristics of Rice Farmers (n=120)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Respondents' age (years)		
21-40	76	63.3
41-60	41	34.2
Above 61	3	2.5
Sex		
Male	70	58.3
Female	50	41.7
Marital status		
Single	16	13.3
Married	73	60.8

Widow	6	5.1
Divorced	25	20.8
Level of Education		
Primary	95	2.4
Secondary	17	40.3
Higher learning	2	38.7
No formal education	6	16.1
Years of Experience		
< 10 years	40	33.3
11-20	40	33.3
21-30	22	18.3
31-40	16	13.3
> 40 years	2	1.8
Farm size		
< 3 hectares	69	57.5
3-7 hectares	47	39.2
> 7 hectares	4	3.3

Source: *Field survey, 2023*

Farmer's access to ICT sources of information among smallholder rice farmers

Based on the data provided in Table 2, it can be observed that 83.3% of farmers utilized information sources through ICT, while the remaining 16.7% did not make use of such sources (Table 2). This suggests that a great deal of At least one farmer possesses an ICT (Information and Communication Technology) tool or device. Information sources, which could enable them to obtain market information without being dependent on intermediaries as they typically do. Farmers should have access to ICT sources of information so that market information may be shared with them in a simple, affordable, and timely manner (Perekwa, Prinsloo and Van Deventer, 2016).

Existing ICT source of information

According to the study, cell phones were the mostly employed ICT information source used by the majority of the participants (50.7%) by farmers to share market information (Table 3). To get market information, this means of obtaining information requires reaching out to friends through a call or text message, relatives, or rice dealers as well as using social media and the internet. Both Nyamba, 2016 and *Olaniyi, 2018*) observed similar findings. One-third of all participants (31%) asserted that they had access to radios, thereby enabling the farmers to employ these of the radio to listen to news on agricultural information, making radios another available source of knowledge. Only 6.3% of respondents who mentioned having a means of accessing the internet, compared to about 12% claimed to have television access (Table 2).

Table 2: Farmer's access to ICT's sources of information and Existing ICT source of information

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Access to ICT		
Yes	100	83.3
No	20	16.7
Total	120	100.0
ICT sources of information		
Mobile	103	50.7
Radio	63	31.0
TV	24	12.0
Internet	13	6.3
Total	203*	100.0

*Multiple responses

Source: *Field survey, 2023*

Factors influencing the access of ICT services among smallholder rice farmers

Access to ICT services in relation to age of the farmer

Since p value > 0.326 is greater than 0.05 levels of significance, the chi-square test,

which has a value of 1.606, proves that the identified discrepancies are insignificant (Table 3). Therefore, there is no solid proof that farmers in the research area who possess access to ICT services see a difference in the percentage of age.

Table 3: Access to ICT services in relation to age of the farmer (n=120)

Variable		Age group		
		21-40	41-60	Above 61
Access to ICT services	Yes	61	36	3
	No	15	5	0
Total		76	41	3

Chi-square = 1.606
P-value = 0.326

Source: *Field survey, 2023*

Access to ICT services in relation to the marital status of the farmer

Chi-square test findings in Table 4 reveal a significant difference ($p = 0.005$) between the research area's farmers' access to ICT services and their marital status. In comparison to the

remainder of the group, farmers who have access to ICT services tended to be married. This shows those married couples have easy access to ICT because they take care of one other's financial, physical, and mental needs together.

Table 4: Access to ICT services in relation to marital status of the farmer (n=120)

Variable		Marital status			
		Single	Married	Widowed	Divorced
Access to ICT services	Yes	14	67	5	14
	No	2	6	1	11
Total		16	73	6	25
Chi-square = 17.399					
P value = 0.005					

Source: *Field survey, 2023*

Access to ICT services in relation to the gender of the farmer

Table 5 findings indicate that there is a substantial distinction between males and women. women's abilities to use ICT services

($p = 0.005$), according to a chi-square test of sex and access to ICT services. The likelihood of men using ICT more frequently than women is shown by this.

Table 5: Access to ICT services in relation to gender (n=120)

Variable		Gender	
		Male	Female
Access to ICT services	Yes	64	36
	No	6	15
Total		70	50
Chi-square = 8.927			
P value = 0.005			

Source: *Field survey, 2023*

Access to ICT services in relation to education level of the farmer

In Table 6, the Chi-Square statistic is 0.897 and ($p = 0.95$) and the null hypothesis is not rejected, since $p > 0.05$. There is little

indication that the level of education varies among farmers that possess the ability to use ICT services for obtaining market information because the degree of education is unlikely to be associated with the use of ICT services.

Table 6: Access to ICT services in relation to education attainment of the farmer (n=120)

Variable		Education attainment			
		Primary	Secondary	Higher learning	No formal education
Access to ICT services	Yes	78	15	2	5
	No	17	2	0	1
Total		95	17	2	6
Chi-square = 0.897					
P value = 0.950					

Source: *Field survey, 2023*

Access to ICT services in relation to the income level of the farmer

Chi square test findings in Table 7 reveal a substantial distinction ($p = 0.0144$) between farmers' income and their capacity to access

ICT services. This shows that compared to people with lesser incomes, farmers are more likely to make use of ICT services to acquire market information if they earn a large amount of money.

Table 7: Access to ICT services in relation to the income level of the farmer (n=120)

Variables		0-199999	200000-499999	500000-799999	800000-1099999	1100000-1399999	1400000-1799999	1800000-2499999	More than 2500000
Access to ICT services	Yes	38	26	12	3	7	6	2	6
	No	6	7	3	2	0	0	0	0
Total		44	33	15	5	7	6	2	6
Chi square = 64.088									
P-value = 0.0144									

Source: Field survey, 2023

Factors Influencing the Use of ICT's in Accessing Agriculture Market Information

The study's second objective was to determine the variables that affect how ICTs is utilized to get marketing information for farming produce. Using a logit regression model, the results were estimated. The logit model's outcomes are indicated in Table 8. In accordance with the results in Table 8, the probability ratio statistic (LR) is 70.93, meaning that the chi-square likelihood ratio is 70.9, with a p-value of 0.0000, demonstrating that the overall model is more superior than a model that is empty or has no signs or signals. The Prob > Chi-square test has a p-value of (0.0000<0.005), which is similar to a threshold of 0.05 to evaluate whether the entire model is statistically noteworthy. The model in question has statistical significance in this instance since the p-value is less than 0.005.

Logit model's data indicates that the farmers' income level, education level, sex, knowledge of and the availability of information and communication technology which have information sources, and awareness of ICT

sources of information, are all positively important factors impacting the farmers' usage of ICTs. The choice of whether to utilize ICT resources of obtaining information is influenced by gender of such household; male farmers are more inclined to than female farmers to use ICT. Education is another household variable that affects the utilization of ICT; the odds ratio is 0.3, the meaning is that among the farmers surveyed, those who have received education comprise 30% to utilize ICTs to acquire market information than farmers that are uneducated or farmers that possess a little degree of education. This demonstrates the critical function in which education has and also plays a notable effect in enhancing knowledge and also capacity to learn new techniques (Widadie and Agustono, 2015). In contrast to the assumptions, a farmer's decision to adopt ICTs is not considerably influenced by his or her age or level of experience. Whereas young farmers are now more likely to utilize ICTs than older farmers, both experienced farmers and less experienced farmers are equally likely to use

ICTs, according to Ayoola and Ayoola (2015). The amount of a farmer's income has a big impact on whether or not they choose to employ ICTs.; farmers who earn more are capable of affording ICT sources of information, able to bear the cost of accessing ICT-based information, or having the financial means to use ICT resources for obtaining information. to pay all operating costs when gaining access to market information than those with lower income levels. Again, contrary to predictions, the utilization to ICT by farmers is not greatly influenced by some of the governing bodies, which then is one of the sources of power, where farmers market their rice, or sources of market information (Adeyemi, Sennuga, Alabuja and Osho-Lagunju, (2023). The opportunity to use ICTs has a positive coefficient (2.045) and is significant at the 5% level (Table 8), suggesting that the increased presence to ICTs improves the market's reachability and

availability of information. According to Kisusi and Sife (2015), rising numbers of small-scale farmers in emerging nations have recently adopted mobile phone technology to improve their participation in accessing agricultural markets. The usage of ICTs has been found to improve information flow among users. By obtaining information about accessible marketplaces and current market pricing, the G.S.M gives smallholder farmers the chance to boost market involvement. As indicated in Table 8, awareness has a positive coefficient of 2.168 at a five percent level of significance, there by suggests that farmers who possess an awareness of how to utilize ICTs more inclined on how they decide to use them to gain market information. This is because awareness helps farmers understand how they can be able to utilize ICTs, so it increases the possibility of adoption by farmers to ICT.

Table 8: Logit results on Factors influencing the market information and Extent of use (Odds) use of ICT's in accessing agriculture

Variables	Co-efficients	Std. Error	P>z	Odds
Age	-0.045	0.1	0.376	1
Sex	-3.244	0.8	0*	0.1
Education	-1.451	0.6	0.015*	0.3
Farmers experience	0.478	0.5	0.337	1.4
Farmers Income	0.000	0	0*	1
Regulatory institutions	0.475	1	0.634	2.1
Awareness	2.168	1.1	0.045*	8.8
Source of power	-1.203	0.7	0.101	0.4
Access to ICT	2.045	0.8	0.006*	8.3
Source of market information	0.208	0.3	0.422	1.3
Constant term	2.31	2.3	0.307	
No. of observation	120			
Log likelihood	- 47.1125			
LR Chi2 (10)	70.93			
Prob>chi-square	0.0000			
Pseudo R2	0.6295			

Note: * indicate significance level of 5%

Source: *Field survey, 2023*

Challenges Encountered by Sampled Farmers When Accessing Market Information

A considerable number of farmers reported feeling challenged by the study area's weak networks and lack of access to mobile networks; this was placed as the foremost major problem. Subsequently, the second challenge is the income level, which is considered a significant issue after the lack of mobile networks, in Table 9. While the majority of the villages where the survey was carried out had access to hydroelectric power (HEP), farmers also voiced complaints about the poor quality of the electricity supply, which received third place. HEP is not well-suited for smallholder farmers and is not affordable to those that have low incomes due to its high initial installation costs. Individuals who possess mobile phones find it

challenging to recharge their batteries at home without electricity, and they cannot watch TV. According to other research (Urassa and Mvena, 2015; Kisusi and Sife, 2015), the absence of electricity in rural regions poses a strong barrier to the use of ICT devices, which contributes to information asymmetry.

According to the survey, owning and using ICT sources of information is somewhat expensive because it requires paying the bill for electricity, purchasing airtime and bundles, and purchasing gadgets that enable information access. Additionally, the fifth-ranked challenge was that some ICTs' information sources didn't satisfy the farmer's information needs at that particular time. This was next to the issue of possessing inaccurate and frequently out-of-date information.

Table 9: Challenges encountered when accessing market information

Challenge	Mean	Overall rank
Outdated information	1.958	7
Incorrect information	1.933	6
Doesn't meet needs of information	1.900	5
Cost	1.875	4
Access to electricity	1.875	3
Income problem	1.875	2
weak network	1.867	1

Source: *Field survey, 2023*

CONCLUSION

The findings of this research demonstrate that a certain majority of respondents in the study areas have easy access to ICTs as a means of obtaining of information (83.3%), whereas only 45% of all farmers with access to ICT's reported using ICTs to acquire market information. According to this, farmers are unaware of how to make use ICTs to acquire market information for their produce. The reason is because most of the farmers' sources of knowledge are middlemen and other farmers like them, accounting for 43.3% and 35%, respectively. This data also looks at mobile phones are the most common ICT source of information which is been utilized by farmers (50.7%). It means that utilization of mobile phone technology provides rice smallholder farmers with quick gateway to market information, facilitating prompt ways to make decisions, lowering marketing costs Farmers in the study area highlighted inadequate access and weak networks as the most challenging obstacle in obtaining market information, with outdated information being the least significant concern. The results from the logit analysis indicated that several factors have a positive influence on accessing market information through ICTs, including farmer gender, education level, income level, awareness of ICTs as a source of information, and the decision to use ICTs for this purpose. Consequently, it can be inferred that cell phones are widely used ICT devices for accessing market information in rural areas. Furthermore, in Abuja, many smallholder farmers are not aware of the various ICT tools available to help them access market information, and as a result, they continue to rely on intermediaries and fellow farmers. According to the study's findings, the primary issues with using ICT as a source of information were insufficient access, a weak network, and a lack of electricity. As a result,

the suggestions listed below are made:

- * The government, in collaboration with the private sector, ought to encourage the accessibility of robust network signals in rural areas, as well as providing a consistent supply of electricity to remote communities is another benefit.
 - * The government ought to maintain and think of initiatives that promote farmers' earnings and offering free education to the poor; these initiatives have a significant impact not only on the development of rural areas but also on promoting the utilization and concoction of agricultural innovation, farming technologies, and marketing among smallholder farmers.
 - * The government ought to promote and enable the usage of mobile phones, which are widely recognized as a well-recognized outlet of information among others, by encouraging a liberal policy for low-cost modern ICT products, particularly mobile phones and airtime.
 - * The government must validate farmer's information units in various wards and village levels to promote simple access to credible information, as well as open up new markets in rural vicinity with the aim to aid the farmers in selling their produce.
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